

Hemiptera, 0 General background, 1 Sternorrhyncha

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Veinal characters in Hemipteroids

PCA+ & CA+ fused
 PCP- is sunken, expressed as a groove
 CP- is either long & parallel, with CA+ as short, recurrent, ending on SCP-
 ScP_ runs often under R&M
 Stem of R is present
 Stem of M is absent
 MA is fused to R (as in Blato- and Holometabola)
 MP may run under R & MA

FW

FW basivenalia

BAA 1+2 is sxtended anteriorly into anal bridge
 And posteriorly into anal bar
 B AA 3+4 and BAP are fused

HW

NEOPTERAN HIND WING VEINAL PATTERNS CHARACTERISTIC FOR LINEAGES

Veinal pattern of Orthoneoptera is the most different. Pleconeoptera share with the rest of Neoptera a similar support for anterior wing margin and presence of the cubital stem, while Blattoneoptera & Hemineoptera & Endoneoptera share derived anojugal lobe starting at the anal fold and a long R & MA fusion supporting long wing axis (see fig. 22).

FW Aphidina: *Triassoaphis cubitus* Evans, 1956 Triassic, Australia

CuA branches fused in Coccioidea

Sternorrhyncha: Amphydidae
 Aphidoidea: *Neoprociphilus aceris* (Monell)

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Recent:
Longistigma caryae (Harris)
 for comparison

Aphidoidea

CSIRO

FW length 53 mm
 width 1.9 mm

E. caugerum

free areolus retained!

FW

Coccoidea: Margarodidae: *Callipappus* sp.

CuA bas produced
arculus reduced

Coccoidea: Margarodidae

Queensland
undetermined

Coccina: Venal scheme of a margarodid, Recent. Original.

brown, smaller than
violet Margarodids.....

